

Thermokinetic Potential in Chemical Reactions

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The generalisation of Li which states that in a non-equilibrium situation thermokinetic potential decreases with time and is minimum in the stationary state, has been experimentally verified for the reversible isomerisation reaction of ammonium thiocyanate and triangular reversible isomerisation reaction of cymene.

Within the domain of validity of Gibb's equation entropy production σ in irreversible processes is expressed as^{1,2} $\sum_i J_i X_i$ where J is the flux and X is the corresponding force. Prigogine¹ has shown that the steady state of no net flow corresponds to the state of minimum entropy production. Since Prigogine's theorem of minimum entropy production is based on linear phenomenological relations and Onsager's reciprocity relations, it cannot be used to evaluate the steady state in the region where fluxes are non-linearly related to thermodynamic forces. With this end in view Glansdroff and Prigogine³ have given a generalisation, according to which, for both linear and non-linear region, the function $m = -\sum_i J_i \dot{X}_i \geq 0$ where \dot{X}_i is the time derivative of the force X_i . The equality holds for the steady state. The validity of the generalisation has been examined in the case of chemical reactions^{4,5}. But it was soon realised⁶ that the generalisation of Glansdroff and Prigogine cannot be used to evaluate the steady state in the non-linear region because the resulting differential equation is difficult to integrate owing to the fact that the constant of integration cannot be evaluated without a prior knowledge of the physical conditions of the steady state.

In view of the non-integrability of the resulting differential equation from Glansdroff and Prigogine's theorem, Li⁷ defined a new function F called thermokinetic potential. F is defined as

$$F = \sum_i \int_0^{X_i} J_i dX_i \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

The function F decreases with time and is minimum in the steady state. The purpose of the present communication is to examine the validity of Li's generalisation for chemical reactions.

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Monomolecular reversible reactions: Let us consider a monomolecular reversible isomerisation reaction,

The reaction rate J and the affinity A for the above reaction (2) can be written as

$$J = k_f(1-x) - k_b x = k_f - (k_f + k_b)x \quad \dots (3)$$

and

$$A = RT \left[\ln \frac{k_f}{k_b} - \ln \frac{x}{1-x} \right] \quad \dots (4)$$

respectively, where k_f and k_b are the rate constants for the forward and backward reactions respectively, $(1-x)$ and x are the amounts of A and B present at any time t , the initial concentration of A being 1. R and T in equation (4) have their usual meaning. The thermokinetic potential F for the chemical reaction (2), can be written as,

$$F = \int_0^A J dA \quad \dots (5)$$

From equations (3) and (4) equation (5) can further be transformed into

$$F = -RT \left[k_f \int_{x_e}^x \frac{dx}{x} + k_b \int_{x_e}^x \frac{dx}{x-1} \right] \quad \dots (6)$$

which on integration yields,

$$F = -RT \left[k_f \ln \frac{x}{x_e} + k_b \ln \frac{1-x}{1-x_e} \right] \quad \dots (7)$$

where x_e is the value of x at equilibrium. Equation (7) can further be rewritten in the form,

$$F = -RT \left[k_f \ln \frac{C_B}{C_B^0} + k_b \ln \frac{C_A}{C_A^0} \right] \quad \dots (8)$$

where C_B and C_A stand for the concentrations of B and A at any time t , and C_B^0 and C_A^0 represent the values of C_B and C_A at equilibrium. Equation (8) can be used to calculate the values of thermokinetic potential at various times from the kinetic data.

The chemical kinetic data⁴ for the reaction

at 170° has been exploited to calculate the values of thermokinetic potential at various times. The value of $(k_f + k_b)$ was calculated graphically from the equation,

$$(k_f + k_b) = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{x_e}{x_e - x} \quad \dots (10)$$

Since the value of equilibrium constant is known from the kinetic data, there was no difficulty in calculating the values of k_f and k_b separately. The values of thermokinetic potential when plotted against time shows that the curve approaches the time axis asymptotically.

Triangular isomerisation reactions : Another interesting case that has been examined is the monomolecular triangular isomerisation of cymene. The kinetics of the reaction, has been studied by Allen, Alfrey and Yats⁸ at 0° who have also calculated the values of k_f and k_b for individual steps of the reaction. The values of the thermokinetic potential for each step of the reaction have been calculated at various times from the kinetic data by making use of equation (8). The values of $\sum_i \int J_i dA_i$ obtained by adding the values of thermokinetic potential for individual steps of the reaction when plotted against time, give the curve approaching the time axis asymptotically.

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